

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part III. Preparation and Properties of N-Aryl Hydroxamic Acid

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22 N-Aryl hydroxamic acids, reported here, were prepared by the condensation of N-aryl hydroxylamine and acid chloride in diethyl ether medium. An aqueous suspension of sodium bicarbonate was added to neutralise the liberated hydrochloric acid. The formation of di-acylated derivative was practically prevented by carrying out the reaction at low temperature, preferably below 0°. These acids have been characterised in terms of analyses, melting points, and ultra-violet and infra-red spectra. These were prepared for possible analytical applications. All of these acids formed chloroform extractable violet complex with vanadium (V) from concentrated hydrochloric acid media.

The preparation and properties of 64 N-aryl hydroxamic acids were reported recently¹⁻³. In this communication further work on 22 N-aryl hydroxamic acids, of which 19 are reported for the first time, is described.

The general methods employed in the syntheses of N-aryl hydroxamic acids are outlined by Yale⁴ in a well documented review article. One of the most widely used procedure for their preparation is based on Schotten-Baumann reaction⁵. This involves the partial acylation of the appropriate N-arylhydroxylamine, I, with acid chloride in aqueous⁶ or benzene¹⁷ or diethyl ether medium²³.

The course of the acylation is very sensitive to the proper choice of experimental conditions, because, otherwise, the concomitant formation of di-substituted hydroxamic acid, III, (and possibly the *o*-acylated arylhydroxylamine, IV) takes place. Most of the workers

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isolated the desired N-mono-derivative, II, from the crude product by tedious and repeated extractions with concentrated ammonium hydroxide, or 5-10% aqueous sodium hydroxide, in which the di-derivative (and any IV, if present) is insoluble, and subsequent acidification with hydrochloric acid. This step of separation is generally annoyingly time-consuming. Besides, the desired product, which is obtained in low yields, is to be further purified by recrystallization from suitable solvents. Recent kinetic studies in this laboratory have revealed that the hydrolysis of N-aryl hydroxamic acids is catalysed both by hydronium and hydroxyl ions.¹⁰ Hence, during the step of separation, where fairly concentrated alkali and acid solutions are used, substantial amounts of desired product are lost due to hydrolysis. This loss is ill afforded in case of acid chlorides which are prohibitively expensive.

In the present study the modified procedure of Priyadarshini and Tandon² is adapted. Thus, freshly prepared N-arylhydroxylamine and vacuum distilled acid chloride in equimolar proportions are reacted at low temperature in diethyl ether medium containing aqueous suspensions of sodium bicarbonate. Under these conditions, the product contains a negligible amount of III and IV and is readily purified by one or two crystallizations from benzene and petroleum ether.

The purity and yield of the product depend vitally on the close adherence to the desired experimental conditions. An excess of acid chloride results in increasing amounts of III and IV, whereas, the use of an excess of N-arylhydroxylamine forms a product which is badly contaminated. Acid catalysed rearrangement of N-arylhydroxylamines and their decomposition into complex products, which are too well-known¹¹, may presumably be responsible for this.

Ultraviolet and infrared spectra of the synthesised hydroxamic acids have been determined for their characterisation. It is believed that these data are not yet reported for the three previously known acids, namely, N-phenyl-1-naphthylaceto-¹², N-phenyl-2, 4-dichlorophenoxyaceto-¹², and N-phenylcapro-¹³ hydroxamic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ultraviolet spectra of hydroxamic acids in spectroscopic grade 95% ethyl alcohol were measured on a Beckmann Model DK-2 ratio recording spectrophotometer using two 10 mm. matched silica cells. Molar absorptivity, determined at the wavelength of maximum absorption, is expressed in units of litres per mole cm.

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STUDIES ON HYDROXAMIC ACIDS. PART III

 TABLE I
 Properties of *N*-Aryl Hydroxymamic Acids

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic Acid	Mol. Formula	Mol. Wt.	M.P. °C	% Yield	λ_{max} (m μ)	$10^{-3}\epsilon$	IR Spectra		Calculated			Found		
								$\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	C	H	N	C	H	N
1	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>n</i> -valero-	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	193.248	71	80	247	10.4	3185	1639	68.37	7.82	7.24	68.28	8.02	7.37
2	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>n</i> -valero-	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	207.274	51	70	248	11.4	3160	1640	69.54	8.27	6.75	69.72	8.42	6.8
3	<i>N</i> -Phenylcapro-	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	207.274	64.5*	75	247	10.3	3115	1613	69.53	8.26	6.76	69.35	7.92	7.09
4	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylcapro-	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	221.300	65	70	252	10.7	3175	1634	70.56	8.65	6.33	70.87	8.86	6.31
5	<i>N</i> -Phenylcaprylo-	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	235.334	64	65	247	9.7	3106	1605	71.45	8.99	5.95	71.03	8.88	5.90
6	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylcaprylo-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	249.350	78	70	248	10.9	3106	1623	72.25	9.30	5.62	72.59	9.32	6.61
7	<i>N</i> -Phenylcapri-	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	263.284	68	85	247	10.3	3175	1639	72.97	9.57	5.32	72.85	9.74	5.14
8	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylcapri-	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	277.401	85	70	248	10.4	3106	1613	73.60	9.81	5.05	73.53	9.43	5.08
9	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylcapri-	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	277.401	49	45	248	10.3	3170	1640	73.60	9.81	5.05	73.85	9.74	4.85
10	<i>N</i> -Phenylmyristo-	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	319.497	87.5	60	247	10.5	3115	1613	75.19	10.41	4.39	75.02	10.28	—
11	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylmyristo-	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{35}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	333.519	79	65	248	10.9	3125	1613	75.62	10.58	4.20	75.88	10.46	4.46
12	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylbeheno-	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{51}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	445.350	92	75	249	12.5	3106	1610	78.21	11.49	3.15	78.24	11.81	3.53
13	<i>N</i> -Phenylcrotono-	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	177.206	111	75	—	—	—	—	67.78	6.26	7.90	67.92	6.63	8.17
14	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylcrotono-	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	191.223	111	80	—	—	—	—	69.09	6.85	7.32	69.33	7.09	7.22
15	<i>N</i> -Phenylundecyleno-	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	275.395	62.5	60	247	12.8	3096	1608	74.14	9.15	5.08	74.08	8.83	5.35
16	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylundecyleno-	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	289.422	76	90	252	11.0	3086	1608	74.70	9.40	4.84	74.33	9.25	5.06
17	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylphenoxyceto-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	257.293	142 ^a	55	250	16.0	3086	1626	70.03	5.87	5.44	69.55	5.96	5.55
18	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-1-naphthylaceto-	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	277.326	121	50	250	12.3	3125	1608	77.96	5.45	5.05	77.96	5.22	5.20
19	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-2,4-dichloro-phenoxyceto-	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}_2$	312.156	165	45	232	17.1	3090	1650	53.86	3.55	4.49	54.24	3.77	4.31
20	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2,4-dichloro-phenoxyceto-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}_2$	326.182	150	40	230	14.8	3125	1653	55.23	4.01	4.32	55.54	4.09	—
21	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylphenoxyceto-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	257.293	119	60	232	8.7	3125	1656	70.03	5.88	5.44	70.35	6.09	5.35
22	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolylphenylaceto-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	241.293	110	70	G A ^a	—	—	1665	74.66	6.27	5.80	74.5	6.28	5.76

^a General adsorption.

Infrared spectra were recorded as mulls in nujol with Perkin Elmer Infracord, Model 137. For comparison and better resolution, a few spectra were recorded with Perkin Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer equipped with sodium chloride optics and calibrated by standard methods.

All the carboxylic acids were commercially available with Koch-Light or B.D.H. These were converted into the corresponding acid chlorides by the action of excess of thionyl chloride. The pure acid chlorides were obtained by distillation under reduced pressure. Their boiling points, melting points, and yields were in good agreement with those given in literature¹⁴.

N-Phenylhydroxylamine¹⁵ and N-*p*-tolylhydroxylamine¹⁶ were freshly prepared and crystallized from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether before use. All attempts to isolate N-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine in the solid state, reported¹⁷ m.p. 44°, failed and, therefore, in further preparations it was used *in situ*.

A typical preparation of N-arylhydroxamic acid is described below.

Into a 500-ml three-necked flask, equipped with a stirrer, dropping funnel, and thermometer, 150 ml. of diethyl ether, 10.9 g. (0.1 mole) of freshly crystallized N-phenylhydroxylamine, and a fine suspension of 12.6 g. (0.15 mole) of sodium bicarbonate in 15-25 ml. of water were added. After the mixture was cooled to 0°, 12.05 g. (0.1 mole) of freshly distilled *n*-valeryl chloride dissolved in 100 ml. of diethyl ether were added drop-wise over a period of 1 hr. Then the reaction mixture was stirred for additional 30 minutes and the temperature was kept low to prevent the side reactions. A white precipitate was obtained, while the ether layer was light yellow. The ethereal layer was separated and ether distilled off under vacuum. The light yellow solid thus obtained was mixed with the precipitated white product and triturated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate in a mortar for about 15 min. to remove acidic impurities. It was filtered off and washed with water. After air-drying it was crystallized from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (boiling range 60-80°) without the use of charcoal. White needle-like crystals were obtained. Yield 15.4 g. (80%, of theoretical), m.p. 70°. The melting point improved to 71° on further crystallizations.

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